

RECONSTRUCTION OF FLOW FLUCTUATIONS FROM MEASUREMENTS OF THE MEAN

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ABSTRACT

In this paper we present approaches for efficiently calculating fluctuating flows, using the flow past a NACA0012 airfoil as an example. The first approach employs data assimilation, to produce Reynolds Averaged Navier Stokes (RANS) equations with a correction term whose steady solution matches a reference mean flow taken from Direct Numerical Simulations (DNS). The benefit of this is that the steady solution is a fixed point, or equilibrium, of the corrected RANS equations; by linearising the corrected RANS equations around this equilibrium, equations for perturbations can be found. We show that since the equilibria are linearly stable, resolvent analysis can be used to recover the large-scale flow fluctuations.

The second approach uses machine learning to extend the capacity of resolvent analysis to recover flow fluctuations to cases for which no DNS reference is available. The correction required for the corrected RANS equations is calculated via a neural network (NN) - the NN is trained on the corrections found via data assimilation in the first approach. The NN is embedded in the flow solver, essentially augmenting the turbulence model.

While promising, we show that the nonlinearity present in the NN can cause numerical issues.

Keywords: Machine learning, turbulence modelling, low-speed aerodynamics

1 INTRODUCTION

This study aims to present a method and framework for the calculation of flow fluctuations that is computationally efficient. The framework is demonstrated for the transitional flow past a NACA0012 airfoil, as an example of a flow with non-trivial fluid mechanics.

The obvious, but most computationally demanding, method for calculating flow fluctuations is direct numerical simulation (DNS), where the governing Navier-Stokes equations are solved for all scales. Examples of this approach for airfoil flows include [1–4]. The computational demand of this approach arises from the stiffness of the equations due to the vast range of time and length scales introduced by the presence of turbulence.

The classic approach to get around this stiffness is the use of Large Eddy Simulation (LES) where small scales are explic-

itly filtered out of the computation and their average impact computed using a sub-grid-scale model [5], or approximating further, the use of Reynolds Averaged Navier-Stokes (RANS) simulations where the impact of turbulent fluctuation is reduced to the introduction of a Reynolds stress (due to the average of products of the fluctuations) in the equations of motion for the long-term, or average, flow. The RANS approach is much less computationally demanding than DNS or LES. However, it suffers from the requirement for a model for the Reynolds stress, since the whole point of the approach is not to calculate the fluctuations which generate these stresses. Here we focus on the eddy viscosity models for the Reynolds stress which, due to the Boussinesq hypothesis, assume the impact of turbulent fluctuation is akin to viscosity and hence produces a turbulent, or eddy, viscosity which varies throughout the flow as the apparent turbulent structure evolves. Extra equations are required to solve for the eddy viscosity and close the system. The validity of a RANS calculation, therefore, depends on the ability of the eddy viscosity model to faithfully recover the true Reynolds stress. Most existing turbulence models are limited in the range of flows that they can successfully capture, especially when complications such as separation and reattachment are present.

Research into methods to improve existing RANS models is therefore an active field. A number of studies have attempted to use measurements, either from physical experiments or selected higher-fidelity simulations, to find improvements to the approximation of the Reynolds stresses. These typically compare the steady solution of the RANS equations (which should recover the mean flow if all of the flow fluctuations are considered in the generation of the Reynolds stress) to the mean flow, and attempt to “correct” the RANS equations by adding terms that force the steady solution and reference mean flow to match. [6] have attempted to extract the eddy viscosity field directly from a temporally-resolved experiment, and [7, 8] have explicitly separated turbulent and coherent fluctuations in an effort to find an eddy viscosity that only incorporated small scale fluctuations; this has the added potential advantage that an unsteady RANS simulation can be used to explicitly find the large scale fluctuations. Another approach, with the advantage that it does not require input from the fluctuations, is to solve for an additional term added to the underlying eddy viscosity model [9].

In this study, we too look for ways to account for the error in eddy viscosity and the error in the Reynolds stress. We add an additional term to the momentum equation, and initially calculate this term via data assimilation using the mean flow from a DNS simulation as a reference. We highlight that the objective here is not simply the recovery of the steady flow field (since we already have the DNS mean); it is the resolution of the additional term, so that we construct a system of equations that admit a steady solution that is equal to the DNS mean flow.

We then linearise this system of equations to find equations that govern the evolution of perturbations about this steady flow

without the need for *ad hoc* assumptions. We show that the perturbations calculated from these equations using resolvent analysis match well with the fluctuations extracted directly from the DNS mean flow - without explicit reference to any temporal information.

Having established the ability to recover fluctuations, we then attempt to find the steady flow and fluctuations simultaneously without explicit reference to DNS by introducing a neural network, imbedded in the flow solver, to provide the additional terms required. We show that this is promising, but research is required to generate a neural network with robust convergence properties.

Section 2 presents a quick overview of the equations and techniques used. Section 3.1 presents example results of the data assimilation process, section 3.2 presents results from the resolvent calculation of perturbations and comparison to DNS fluctuations, and section 3.3 presents results of the embedded neural network solver. A summary and concluding remarks are given in section 4.

2 METHODOLOGY

2.1 Problem setup: the NACA0012 airfoil

While the focus of this study is the framework within which to reconstruct flow fluctuations, we apply this framework to the incompressible freestream flow past a NACA0012 airfoil. The typical case studied has the airfoil at an angle of attack $\alpha = 2^\circ$; we investigate other angles of attack towards the end of this paper. The freestream flow has velocity U , the airfoil has chord length c , and the fluid has kinematic viscosity ν . The Reynolds number is set such that $Re = Uc/\nu = 5 \times 10^4$. This is low enough to be accessible to DNS to provide reference data, but high enough to generate a transitional flow with turbulent fluctuations which can be problematic for traditional turbulence models to capture.

The three-dimensional direct numerical simulations (DNS) of this flow were conducted using the spectral element solver Nek5000 [10]. The two-dimensional Reynolds-averaged Navier-Stokes simulations (RANS), data assimilation, and machine-learning augmented RANS models were implemented and ran using the finite element solver freeFEM++ [11].

2.2 The baseline RANS model

The objective of this study is to produce a model that can efficiently capture flow fluctuations. The “baseline” model from which we start is the RANS equations including the Boussinesq hypothesis resulting in an eddy viscosity which produces equa-

tions of motion

$$\begin{aligned} \partial_t \langle u \rangle + (\langle u \rangle \cdot \nabla) \langle u \rangle + \nabla \langle P \rangle - \nabla \cdot \left[2 \left(\frac{1}{\text{Re}} + \langle v_t \rangle \right) S(\langle u \rangle) \right] &= 0 \\ \nabla \cdot \langle u \rangle &= 0, \end{aligned} \quad (1)$$

where ∂_t denotes the time derivative, angle brackets $\langle \rangle$ denote averaged quantities, u is the velocity field, P is the modified pressure field (to incorporate the expansion/dilation Reynolds stress), v_t is the turbulent, or eddy, viscosity, and $S(\langle u \rangle)$ is the rate of strain tensor for the averaged field. The eddy viscosity is found via the one-equation Spalart-Allmaras (SA) turbulence model [12], augmented with the Bas-Cakmakcioglu Modified (BCM) intermittency function [13] as a transition model. We therefore refer to this baseline model as the SA-BCM model.

2.3 Data assimilation for a corrected RANS model

Our approach to capturing flow fluctuations is similar in ethos to the typical RANS approach; we treat the flow as consisting of a mean and a fluctuation about that mean. The novelty here is approximate the fluctuations as, initially, a *linear* perturbation about the mean. For this approach to be valid, without the need for *ad hoc* modelling or assumptions, the mean needs to be a *steady* solution; the key idea, therefore, is to find a system for which this holds.

We find this system using data assimilation. The basic process is as follows. A steady correction term is added to the SABCM equation for the eddy viscosity. This can be expressed as

$$\partial_t \langle v_v \rangle + T(\langle u \rangle, \langle v_v \rangle) = g_v \langle v_v \rangle, \quad (2)$$

where $\langle v_v \rangle$ is the Spalart viscosity variable (from which v_t is calculated), T an operator that defines the original SABCM model, and $g_v \langle v_v \rangle$ is the additional correction term. Steady solutions of the resulting equations are sought (with no correction term, the solution found is a steady solution of the baseline model). We then search for the correction term that results in a steady solution which matches a reference mean flow obtained via DNS (note that by definition, when solving for steady solutions the time derivative terms in equations (1) and (2) is excluded). The correction term $g_v \langle v_v \rangle$ is found by minimising a variable J defined as

$$J(\langle u \rangle) = \frac{1}{2} \int_{\Omega_m} (\bar{u}_d - \langle u \rangle) \cdot (\bar{u}_d - \langle u \rangle) d\Omega_m, \quad (3)$$

where \bar{u}_d is the reference DNS mean velocity field and Ω_m is the measurement domain. Note that the steady velocity field $\langle u \rangle$ is

a function of $g_v \langle v_v \rangle$, so that the minimum of J can be found by tuning this term. For this study, we employed an adjoint-based optimisation scheme implemented using the discretised forms of the equations of motion, similar to the scheme described in [14].

We note that the primary outcome of this process is not the steady velocity field $\langle u \rangle$ (since we already have the true mean \bar{u}_d); rather, it is the correction term $g_v \langle v_v \rangle$, which, by modifying the eddy viscosity, leads to the additional stress required for the corrected steady RANS equations to produce a solution that matches the DNS mean flow.

2.4 Linear stability and resolvent analyses

The corrected RANS equations produced by the data assimilation and outlined in equations (1) and (2), can be used to form evolution equations for linear perturbations around the steady solution which consists of the corrected steady velocity field $\langle u \rangle \simeq \bar{u}_d$, and the associated pressure $\langle P \rangle$ and eddy viscosity $\langle v_t \rangle$. We designate this steady state solution as $\langle q \rangle$.

We define the total solution of equations (1) and (2) as $q = \langle q \rangle + q'$. Substituting, and collecting first order terms results in

$$\begin{aligned} \partial_t u' + (\langle u \rangle \cdot \nabla) u' + (u' \cdot \nabla) \langle u \rangle + \nabla p' \\ - \nabla \cdot \left[2 \left(\frac{1}{\text{Re}} + \langle v_t \rangle \right) S(u') \right] \\ = f'. \end{aligned} \quad (4)$$

Note that in this formulation, terms involving the perturbations of the eddy viscosity (including the impact of introducing perturbations on the additional correction term $g_v \langle v_v \rangle$) are grouped into a forcing term f' and moved to the right-hand side of equation (4).

Formed this way, equation (4) presents a linear equation for the evolution of perturbations, subject to an external (and unknown) forcing that arises due to the fluctuation of additional stresses induced by the added eddy viscosity due to the additional correction term. The homogeneous equation (i.e., where this external force, f' , is assumed to be zero) can be cast as an eigenvalue problem, which is a classical linear stability analysis. We note that for the flows of this study, the linear stability analysis (excluded for brevity) shows no unstable modes which is physically consistent with the concept of the mean flow being steady. The fact that the steady flow which coincides with the true mean flow is stable suggests that resolvent analysis is valid to ascertain, or in some sense recover, the linear fluctuations that generated the reference mean flow.

Resolvent analysis assumes the external forcing (in this case q') can be represented as harmonic functions, i.e., $f' = \hat{f} e^{i\omega t}$ and $q' = \hat{q} e^{i\omega t}$. The aim, then, is to find the forcing field \hat{f} which produces the largest \hat{u} (where \hat{u} is contained within \hat{q}). Similar to other transfer function or impedance problems, the aim is to find the input field (or ‘‘forcing mode’’) which produces the largest

gain (or “output mode”) for a given forcing frequency. In this way, a “resolvent spectrum” can be constructed, where the gain is plotted as a function of frequency.

In this study we construct the resolvent spectrum, as well as present the output mode shapes at the dominant frequencies in this spectrum which are expected to represent the modes of the dominant fluctuations of the flow. Note that this process arrives at these fluctuations with reference only to the DNS mean flow \bar{u}_d .

2.5 Field inversion machine learning

A final aspect of this study is to investigate the potential to calculate both the mean flow and dominant fluctuations for cases where no reference data is available. For this task, we employ field inversion machine learning [15], to construct a neural network that can output the required additional correction term g_v , from an input only of the steady flow. This NN is then embedded in the RANS flow solver, so that the steady solution velocity, pressure and eddy viscosity fields, as well as the steady additional correction term, can be solved simultaneously.

Rather than passing the primitive variable values at each mesh point as the inputs to the NN, we construct a series of quantities from both gradients and primitive values as inputs, which can help to avoid non-physical outputs [16].

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 Data-assimilated steady flows

Figure 1 shows results from the data assimilation process for the example case where $\alpha = 2^\circ$. The streamwise component of the calculated steady flow is shown in figure 1a. The separation and recirculation over the rear of the suction side (top) of the airfoil is clearly shown. The difference between the steady flow, and the reference DNS mean flow, is shown in figure 1b. It is clear that the difference is minimal, with only a small region immediately downstream of the trailing edge showing a discernable difference. The recirculation region is well captured, as the steady flow and the reference mean flow are practically identical in this region. The additional correction term is shown in figure 1c. It is clear that the recirculation region is the location of the largest correction. This is, perhaps, not surprising; the uncorrected SABC model is not able to capture the reattachment of the flow in this region and so it is here that the correction needs to be the strongest.

3.2 Comparison of measured fluctuations with calculated perturbations

Section 3.1 shows that the data assimilation process is capable of producing a system whose steady solution closely matches the reference mean flow. In this section, we compare how resolvent modes - which are calculated from equations formed by

FIGURE 1. RESULTS OF THE DATA ASSIMILATION FOR THE CASE OF $\alpha = 2^\circ$. (a) COLOUR CONTOURS OF THE MAGNITUDE OF THE RESULTING VELOCITY FIELD. (b) COLOUR CONTOURS OF THE DIFFERENCE BETWEEN THE RESULTING VELOCITY FIELD AND THE REFERENCE MEAN FIELD FROM DNS. (c) CONTOURS OF THE ADDITIONAL CORRECTION TERM, SHOWING IT IS FOCUSED IN THE NEAR WAKE AND OUTSIDE THE REGION OF REVERSED FLOW UPSTREAM OF THE TRAILING EDGE.

linearising this system about this steady flow - can closely approximate the fluctuation measured from a fully nonlinear three-dimensional DNS.

We recall that the aim of a resolvent analysis is to calculate pairs of input-output modes for an assumed-harmonic forcing at a particular frequency. The modes discovered by this analysis are the input which leads to the largest gain, and the response of the system to this input. We define the gain as

$$\sigma^2 = \frac{\langle \hat{q}, \hat{q} \rangle_q}{\langle \hat{f}, \hat{f} \rangle_f} \quad (5)$$

which is the ratio of the inner products of the output and input (note that if the output is only the velocity, this inner product is directly proportional to the kinetic energy of the output).

FIGURE 2. (a) THE RESOLVENT SPECTRUM, CALCULATED FROM THE CORRECTED RANS SOLUTION $\langle q \rangle$. (b) THE SPOD SPECTRUM, EXTRACTED FROM THE TIME DEPENDENT DNS SOLUTION u_d . BOTH DISPLAY EQUISPACED SPIKES IN THE RANGE OF NONDIMENSIONAL FREQUENCIES $2 < St < 4$. THE MARKERS IN BOTH PLOTS (\square) INDICATE COMMON FREQUENCIES (WHICH COINCIDE WITH THREE PEAKS ($St = 2.3333, 2.8333, 3.3333$) AND ONE LOCAL MINIMUM ($St = 3.5833$) IN THE DNS SPOD SPECTRUM) FOR WHICH THE RESOLVENT AND SPOD MODES ARE COMPARED IN FIGURE 3.

Figure 2a plots this gain for the primary resolvent mode at each frequency (other secondary modes have gains at least two orders of magnitude smaller). The resulting spectrum is characterised by a series of approximately equi-spaced spikes in the range of nondimensional frequencies (quantified by $St = fc/U$) $2 < St < 4$.

An essentially direct comparison can be made between the resolvent spectrum and the spectral proper orthogonal decomposition (SPOD) spectrum that is extracted from the fully nonlinear three-dimensional DNS. It has been shown [17] that if the external forcing can be considered white noise, then the SPOD should return a spectrum that are in direct correspondence with the resolvent spectrum. Therefore, figure 2b plots the SPOD spectrum. SPOD progresses by first taking the Fourier spectrum of a time-varying field, typically applying Welch’s method (i.e., breaking the time-varying signal into an ensemble of smaller, overlapping blocks and then taking the Fourier transform of each block). The components at a given frequency ω from each block are then

grouped, and proper orthogonal decomposition (POD) applied to extract the most energetic mode, or modes, at that frequency ω (note that if the time series is truly ergodic, there will be only one mode at each ω). Details of this process can be found in [18] The energy of each mode, λ , is therefore a measure of the importance of that mode, and therefore of the importance of λ . The SPOD spectrum is a series of curves: the first curve is λ for the leading mode at each frequency as a function of frequency; the second curve is λ for the second mode at each frequency; and so on. The spectrum shown in figure 2b plots only the leading mode curve; the energy of the secondary modes is orders of magnitude less than that of the first.

The SPOD spectrum compares well to the resolvent spectrum in terms of frequency content, as it too has a series of approximately equispaced spikes in the range $2 < St < 4$. There is a slight shift in the values of the frequencies at the spikes compared to the resolvent analysis result, but only very slightly.

A further comparison can be made by comparing the mode shapes calculated by the resolvent analysis and the modes extracted from the DNS via SPOD. We compare the streamwise velocity component of the leading modes at four frequencies in figure 3. The first three frequencies are the first three frequency spikes in the DNS-generated SPOD spectrum, while the fourth is a local minima. The values of frequencies are marked with open squares in both the SPOD and resolvent spectra. While the scaling of the absolute amplitude of the resolvent modes is a topic of active research [19], the topologies of the four selected modes are shown to compare well between the resolvent and SPOD analyses.

The resolvent analysis is therefore shown to correctly return the multiple frequencies present in the DNS simulation, and to return modes of the correct structure to represent the spatial distribution of fluctuations. It essentially recovers the structure of the temporal fluctuations. We recall that the resolvent analysis achieves this with an input of only the reference mean flow; no explicit temporal information is required.

3.3 Towards a generalised model with machine learning

The previous sections have shown that: the corrected RANS equations, when a suitable additional correction term $g_v \langle v_v \rangle$ is added, realise a steady solution that matches the DNS reference mean; the additional correction term $g_v \langle v_v \rangle$ can be found via data assimilation; linearising the resulting equations about the steady solution allows a resolvent analysis to recover the primary fluctuations in the flow to be recovered. The significant result is that once the corrected RANS equations are constructed (i.e, a solution $\langle q \rangle$ and additional correction term $g_v \langle v_v \rangle$ are found), the proceeding linearisation and resolvent analysis can recover the flow fluctuations.

In this section, we attempt to further generalise this by mov-

FIGURE 3. THE STREAMWISE VELOCITY COMPONENT OF THE RESOLVENT MODES CALCULATED FROM THE CORRECTED RANS STEADY FLOW (LEFT) AND SPOD MODES EXTRACTED FROM THE TIME-DEPENDENT DNS (RIGHT). THE LINEAR RESOLVENT MODES HAVE BEEN NORMALISED TO AID COMPARISON. THE TOPOLOGIES OF THE RESOLVENT AND SPOD MODES AT ALL FREQUENCIES MATCH WELL.

ing to a framework where we remove the reliance on an explicit reference case or mean flow. Instead of finding the additional correction term by data assimilation, we train a neural network (NN) to calculate the additional correction term g_v at a given location in the flow, given the underlying flow field $\langle q \rangle$. The input data are not simply the values of the solution at a given location, but 10 quantities found by combining both primitive values and gradients; this process helps to ensure a more robust solution (for example, ensuring Galilean invariance). Details can be found in [16]. The input data are taken from a series of data assimilation simulations at angles of attack $0 \leq \alpha \leq 2$ in steps $\Delta\alpha = 0.5$.

Of course, the input data for the NN, being the steady flow, is unknown at the start of a simulation. The NN needs to be embedded in the flow solver, so that the steady flow *and* the additional stress can be solved simultaneously. The equations of motion become essentially homogenised, i.e.,

$$\partial_t \langle v_v \rangle + T(\langle u \rangle, \langle v_v \rangle) = \langle g_{NN}(\langle q \rangle) \rangle \langle v_v \rangle, \quad (6)$$

because the additional correction term returned by the NN is a function of the steady solution. Solving equation (6) the momentum and continuity equations (1) provides the solution $\langle q \rangle$ and the additional correction term $\langle g_{NN}(\langle q \rangle) \rangle \langle v_v \rangle$.

Figure 4 shows results from this embedded NN solver. Four cases are shown. Cases $\alpha = 0^\circ$, 1° and 2° provided data for the training set used for the NN, whereas the case at $\alpha = 0.25^\circ$ did not. The left column of the figure shows the streamwise component of the steady velocity field, and the right column shows the x-component of the additional stress. The results are promising, with the three cases for $\alpha \leq 1^\circ$ fully converging to machine precision. The cases which provided training data, for which there is a data assimilated case to compare to, return essentially the same solution for both the flow and the additional stress. This provides confidence that the case for which no data assimilated case exists, $\alpha = 0.25^\circ$, is accurate.

However, the case for $\alpha = 2^\circ$ which has been used as an exemplar for this study, is more complicated. On one hand, the images of the steady flow and the additional correction term

FIGURE 4. RESULTS FROM THE CORRECTED RANS SOLVER WITH THE NEURAL NETWORK EMBEDDED TO SOLVE FOR $\langle f \rangle$ SIMULTANEOUSLY WITH $\langle q \rangle$ FOR ANGLES OF ATTACK $\alpha = 0^\circ, 0.25^\circ, 1^\circ, \text{ and } 2^\circ$. LEFT: X-COMPONENT OF THE STEADY VELOCITY FIELD $\langle u \rangle$. RIGHT: X-COMPONENT OF THE ADDITIONAL STRESS $\langle g_{NN} \rangle$. THE CASES $\alpha \leq 1^\circ$ CONVERGE REGARDLESS OF WHETHER THE VALUE OF α PROVIDED TRAINING DATA OR NOT, HOWEVER THE $\alpha = 2^\circ$ CASE CAN ONLY PARTIALLY CONVERGE WITH FURTHER ITERATION CAUSING DIVERGENCE. THIS IS DESPITE THE FACT $\alpha = 2^\circ$ PROVIDED TRAINING DATA FOR THE NN.

returned by the embedded NN solver shown in figure 4 compare well with those from the data-assimilated corrected RANS shown in figure 1. On the other hand, we note that this solution is only partially converged; this case initially converged to a small, but non-negligible, residual, then further iterations saw the solver diverge. The results shown in figure 4 are those for the smallest residual found. This is despite this case providing data

to the training set.

We propose this numerical instability is due to the highly nonlinear properties of the NN. It may be expected that since the $\alpha = 2^\circ$ case provided data to the training set, the NN would simply return the additional correction term required for the corresponding steady flow. However, we recall that the steady flow is not available *a priori*; early iterations will therefore have some

approximation of this steady flow as an input to the NN. If these early iterations are far enough from the true steady flow in the model phase space, then the NN can diverge.

Improving the convergence properties of the NN is required, and will be the focus of future research.

4 SUMMARY AND CONCLUSION

In this paper we have presented a method for recovering the primary fluctuations of a flow, demonstrated for the transitional flow past a NACA0012 airfoil at $Re = 5 \times 10^4$ and small angles of attack α . The basis of the method is the formation of a set of equations for which a steady solution matches the mean of the true solution, and then linearising this set of equations around the steady solution to provide equations for the perturbations which can represent the flow fluctuations.

In a first step, the classic RANS equations are corrected by adding an additional stress term which is found via data assimilation, using a reference mean flow calculated from DNS. The linearisation of the equations found this way are amenable to resolvent analysis, and we have shown that this analysis is able to recover the spectrum and structure of the primary fluctuations of the flow.

Having established that the resolvent analysis can recover the fluctuations if the underlying steady solution is known, we progress to a second step where we attempt to find the underlying steady solution without explicit reliance on a reference mean flow. To achieve this, we train a neural network to provide the additional stress required for the corrected RANS equations, and embed this neural network in the flow solver. We show that the corrected RANS solver with embedded neural network is promising, returning results matching reference cases when the angle of attack (and the resulting additional correction term) is small. However, numerical convergence issues arise as the angle of attack (and the additional correction term) increases. We suggest this is due to the highly nonlinear structure of the neural network, and future work will focus on improving its convergence properties.

ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

RP and MS acknowledge the financial support provided through the Aerostructures Innovation and Research Hub (AIRHub) at Swinburne University of Technology. JL acknowledges that this research was undertaken with the assistance of resources from the National Computational Infrastructure (NCI Australia), an NCRIS enabled capability supported by the Australian Government. A portion of this work was performed on the OzSTAR national facility at Swinburne University of Technology. The OzSTAR program receives funding in part from the Astronomy National Collaborative Research Infrastructure Strategy (NCRIS) allocation provided by the Australian Government,

and from the Victorian Higher Education State Investment Fund (VHESIF) provided by the Victorian Government.

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